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Innovative Climate-Control System to Extend Range of Electric Vehicles and Improve Comfort (XERIC)

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Report:

XERIC’s 5th Newsletter

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Summary:

This is the fifth of XERIC’s e-newsletters. The e-newsletters are released twice a year.

This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created and sent and who the subscribers are.

The newsletter is then displayed. It reaches more than 65 institutions, among which 30 industries and 14 academic organisations.

The appendices display the full versions of the editorial and the 3 interviews introduced in the newsletter.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
12.05.2017	Mathilde BOUCHER (EMH)	Preparation version 1 (V1)	

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Content

1. Creating and sending e-newsletters	3
2. Subscribers	3
3. Newsletter 5.....	3
4. Appendices.....	7

1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to the *WordPress* Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically **as emails**. The software splits the mailing list in several sub-lists so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Subscribers

Mailing lists were created in 2015 for the different communication purposes that we may have for the XERIC project. The starting point was each of the XERIC partners and their own professional mailing lists. There were 123 subscribers in 2015. The total number of subscribers rose to 150 in May 2016, then to 268 in December 2016 and finally to 306 since November 2017.

The newsletter reaches now more than 65 institutions, among which 30 industries and 14 academic organizations.

XERIC's fifth newsletter was sent to all 306 subscribers.

People can unsubscribe thanks to an "unsubscribe" button at the bottom of the e-newsletter.

3. Newsletter 5

Please click [here](#) to read XERIC's 5th newsletter online.

Screenprints of the newsletter are displayed on the next pages.

See appendices for all the links to pdf documents that can be opened when browsing the newsletter online.

Newsletter 5 - November 2017

Follow us [@XERICproject](https://twitter.com/XERICproject)

and use #XERIC when you tweet a message related to the project !

Editorial by Project Coordinator

Welcome to our fifth newsletter!

XERIC is now entering the finishing straight to reach its objective of developing an energy-friendly climate-control system for electric vehicles capable to reduce by more than 50% the energy used for passenger comfort all over the year.

We just had our 6th project meeting last week in Genoa, followed by the 2nd Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) meeting and the 3rd XERIC Workshop. [...]

Now the prototype is real, the members of the project are ready to present their work to potential industrial partners, in order to move with their help from the lab (TRL4) to the systems validation in real-world working conditions and, hopefully, to the market.

[...] [Read full editorial](#)

Enjoy this issue !

Nino Gaeta - GVS spa - XERIC's Coordinator

Successful workshop during the Genoa Smart Week !

XERIC took the opportunity to organize its 3rd workshop in the frame of the third edition of the [Genoa Smart Week](#), which took place from 20th to 24th November 2017 and received over 200 participants each day from local, national and international institutions.

After a short reminder of the Horizon 2020 context, the XERIC technology and its applications in various fields (e.g. for cars, boats, buildings) have been presented, as well as heating and smart preconditioning systems developed for electric vehicles in the frame of JOSPEL and OPTEMUS.

This workshop allowed to reach a large targeted audience and even to initiate contacts for new collaborations between research and industry. Now that the XERIC prototype is real and functional, the objective is to find industrial partners interested to move from the lab to the market!

[Read more](#)

(with links to upload the presentation materials & watch a short video in italian)

Clustering around Dissemination Activities

The European Commission has created a new EU-funded dissemination service to help projects maximize their impact on market: the Common Dissemination Booster (CDB) offers free of charge

services to clusters of projects and shows them how best to disseminate to end-users, with an eye on exploitation opportunities.

XERIC, together with JOSPEL and OPTEMUS applied for 3 CDB services: Portfolio Identification Service, Stakeholder/End-user mapping and Portfolio Dissemination Plan Development. **The applications have already been accepted and services are expected to begin in early 2018!**

Get to know the XERIC team members - INTERVIEWS

Claudia CATTANEO

TICASS, Italy

Dr Claudia CATTANEO works at TICASS since 2011, with the role of project manager. She is currently in charge for the general management of the activities led by TICASS in the frame of XERIC

In her opinion, "one focal innovative point in the project is bringing together research labs and industry, encouraging the technology transfer and the

interdisciplinary approach."

[Read the full interview](#)

Oleg ILIEV

Fraunhofer ITWM, Germany

With more than 30 years of experience in Mathematical Modeling and Computer Simulation for academic research and solving industrial problems, Pr. Dr. Oleg ILIEV is a senior scientist at ITWM and Adjunct Professor at the Faculty of Mathematics at the Technical University of Kaiserslautern.

He witnesses that "with the creative and collaborative efforts of all involved partners, the bottlenecks are

overcome".

[Read the full interview](#)

Fausto LENTINI

GVS S.P.A, Italy

Dr Fausto LENTINI is an expert in filtration media and in automotive filters. Involved in the frame of XERIC, he is in charge of assembling the 3F-CMC.

"I really like to work collaboratively to solve problems, developing filters in my actual position."

[Read the full interview](#)

Discover XERIC partners' expertise

Fraunhofer-ITWM

The Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics (ITWM - Germany) is one of the more than 60 institutes of the Fraunhofer Society for applied research. The ITWM has gained a high reputation in mathematical research for industrial and commercial applications.

ITWM's participation in XERIC is mainly driven by the department of Flow and Material Simulation (about 30 employees). ITWM is responsible for the design of a small scale prototype of the climate control system. ITWM is also involved in modelling efforts aiming at understanding, quantifying and thus preventing frost formation.

[Read more](#)

[Click here to read more about XERIC](#)

4. Appendices

- Editorial by Nino Gaeta, XERIC's coordinator
- Link to read the news about the 3rd workshop organized in Genoa: <http://xeric.eu/successful-3rd-workshop/>
- 3 interviews
 - Claudia CATTANEO, from TICASS
 - Oleg ILIEV, from Fraunhofer ITWM
 - Fausto LENTINI, from GVS

XERIC's technology now ready to move from the lab to the market!

Welcome to our fifth newsletter.

XERIC is now entering the finishing straight to reach its objective of developing an energy-friendly climate-control system for electric vehicles capable to reduce by more than 50% the energy used for passenger comfort all over the year.

We just had our **6th project meeting** last week in Genoa, followed by the **2nd Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) meeting and the 3rd XERIC Workshop**.

Four 3F-CMC prototypes have been manufactured by GVS with the support of TICASS, UNIGE, ITWM, FRIGOMAR, UDE and VITO, and are currently tested in the TICASS laboratories. The full XERIC CCS has been assembled and FRIGOMAR is starting the test phase in a dedicated climatic chamber, which enable to test different indoor and outdoor conditions.

Now the prototype is real, the members of the project are ready to present their work to potential industrial partners, in order to move with their help from the lab (TRL4) to the systems validation in real-world working conditions and, hopefully, to the market.

We took indeed the opportunity to present in Genoa our XERIC innovative technology in front of industrial representatives and in the framework of the 3rd workshop untitled **"Breakthrough Technologies in Climate Control Systems"**, which was hosted by the third edition of Genoa Smart Week. Over 200 participants each day from local, national and international institutions attended the event. Clustering with JOSPEL and OPTEMUS European projects, this workshop allowed us to reach a large targeted audience and even to initiate contacts for new collaborations between research and industry.

More on page 2

Also, dissemination of the project results and ambition is proceeding quite well. I am happy that EC has granted to XERIC's, together with JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects, the support of the **Common Dissemination Booster**, a brand-new service from the European Commission. The booster encourages projects to come together to identify a common portfolio of results and shows them how best to disseminate to end-users, with an eye on exploitation opportunities. It will enable us to deepen and strengthen our dissemination activities.

In this edition of our newsletter, you'll also get a glimpse into the daily working life of Claudia Cattaneo from TICASS, Fausto Lentini from GVS and Oleg Iliev from Fraunhofer-ITWM, all three involved in XERIC.

Finally, we welcome any comments or suggestion from all people interested in our project and we invite you to read more about it on our website: www.xeric.eu. Don't forget to follow us on Twitter [@XERICproject](https://twitter.com/XERICproject)!

Enjoy this issue!

Nino Gaeta
GVS SPA
XERIC's Coordinator

European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Dr Claudia CATTANEO**

Expert in membrane industrial application & project manager
at TICASS, Italy

Dr Claudia CATTANEO

works at TICASS since 2011, with the role of project manager within financed projects and private commissions.

In XERIC, she is in charge for the general management of the activities led by TICASS (respect of the time-line and financial aspects). Two experts specifically hired and two Departments of UNIGE are also involved in the project, so Claudia is representing the “point of convergence” for all types of information, incoming and outgoing, about technical, financial and administrative topics.

Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself?

I come from Recco, a small town on the East Riviera of Liguria. I completed my Master degree in Environmental Engineering in 2001 at University of Genoa and then I had a Ph. D. in Methods and Technologies for the Environmental Monitoring.

I worked for many years at University of Genoa as researcher assistant on different topics related to wastewater depuration techniques and environmental and health risk assessment for contaminated sites. I joined TICASS in 2011, when the consortium launched its activities, with the role of project manager within financed projects (H2020, MED, Life+, etc.) and private commissions, dealing with environmental topics with a particular focus on waste and water issues.

"A common point of my work days is the continuous interaction with different subjects"

I'm a contact point for TICASS's associates for technical issues and I usually work together with the whole TICASS team in drafting proposals for financed projects about innovation and industrial research. I am also involved as a teacher in training activities organised by TICASS.

What is appealing to you being a researcher? How challenging is it?

In my opinion, to be a researcher is appealing because you have the possibility to interface different issues and to know different aspects of the same problem.

I think that the main challenge for a researcher is to find innovative solutions to conventional problems in order to achieve relevant results, that means basically to go beyond the state-of-art.

What does your daily job look like?

I do not have a typical day at work, but I think that a common point of my work days is the continuous interaction with different subjects, i.e. academic figures, entrepreneurs, technicians and administrative officers.

So my work day is usually very dynamic! My main activities go from internal meetings to coordinate, to set up and write documents and reports for contracts in being, meetings with third subjects, technical visits to plants and sometimes also activities at TICASS laboratory.

"I'm a contact point for TICASS's associates for technical issues and I usually work together with the whole TICASS team"

What excites you in the XERIC project?

I was internally selected to be involved in XERIC because of my technical skills and

my previous experience in European projects. In my opinion, one focal innovative point in the XERIC project is bringing together research labs and industry, encouraging the technology transfer and the interdisciplinary approach.

"To be a researcher is appealing because you have the possibility to know different aspects of the same problem"

What are, according to you, the major challenges to be overcome in XERIC?

XERIC is a very challenging project. Each single partner is in charge of activities that must achieve relevant results. So anyone has his own specific challenge, according to competences and skilled experience.

Basically, the major challenges are related to the achievement of these partial results, in accordance with time and costs, in order to achieve the final one, which is the development of the innovative climate conditioning system with improved performances and the evaluation of its potential in the automotive market.

What are you expecting from the project?

I think that one positive output expected from XERIC could be to enlarge the field application of the 3F-CMC technology to other sectors, i.e. buildings, greenhouses etc... This will improve the competitiveness of enterprises involved in the project.

Are you participating in other international projects? Can you talk about them and explain the role you play?

Nowadays, I'm also involved in a European project called FORCE (Innovation action H2020), that aims to minimize the leakage of materials from the linear economy and work towards a circular economy. The city of Genoa participates for the wood waste and engage enterprises, citizens and academia to create and develop eco-innovative solutions. As TICASS, we are implementing an integrated wood management Urban Laboratory, with the aim to create innovative market applications and test new technology applications.

Then, from 2018 I'll be involved as project manager for TICASS in a new incoming project, about the management of wastes coming from the fishing, aquaculture sectors and harbor activities, involving different actors located in some regions in Italy and France.

"One positive output expected from XERIC could be to enlarge the field of application for the 3F-CMC technology to other sectors, i.e. buildings, greenhouses, etc."

Thanks for your time Claudia. All the best for XERIC and your other projects!

Claudia's skills

Chemical engineering; industrial membrane application, project management

TICASS, a partner in the XERIC project

TICASS – acronym for **Innovative Technologies for Environmental Control and Sustainable Development** - is a non-profit Consortium established in March 2010, composed of research authorities and large, medium and small companies.

TICASS performs, promotes and enhances research activities, as well as **transferring excellence technologies in the "Energy and Environment" area** with regards to **Sustainable Development and Quality of Life**. The consortium main goal is to **widen knowledge and introduce innovative technologies** by the cross-border cooperation, with universities and other public and private bodies.

TICASS carries out XERIC's research tasks by addressing and coordinating synergically the **work of TICASS and UNIGE teams**. TICASS in collaboration with UNIGE has carried out for many years theoretical and experimental research on air dehumidification/conditioning with liquid desiccants and membrane contactors. XERIC capitalizes on their recent research results internationally patented by the Genoa University: the **three Fluids Combined Membrane Contactors (3F-CMC) components**.

XERIC in brief

XERIC is a European Research & Innovation Project

Start date: 1st June 2015

End date: 31st May 2018

Number of partners: 8

Coordinator:

Dr. Eng. S. GAETA
GVS spa, Italy

Programme:

H2020-GV-2014

Project Reference: 653605

Interview with **Prof. Dr Oleg ILIEV**

Senior scientist at the Fraunhofer Institute
for Industrial Mathematics - ITWM, Germany

Pr. Dr. Oleg ILIEV

is a senior scientist at ITWM and Adjunct Professor at the Faculty of Mathematics at the Technical University of Kaiserslautern.

With more than 30 years of experience in Mathematical Modeling and Computer Simulation for academic research and solving industrial problems, he coordinates ITWM's participation in the XERIC project and participates in the work on most of the tasks assigned to ITWM.

Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself?

I was born in Bulgaria and since my school years the mathematics was my favorite subject. With a grant from the Bulgarian Government, I was lucky to study computational mathematics in Moscow State University. This was also a chance to meet and to attend lectures from some of the top mathematicians of the 20-th century. I got my PhD in mathematics and physics also from Moscow State University.

What is appealing to you being a researcher?

Being a researcher is a great pleasure, and at the same time a hard work. Most of the time the researcher is under stress.

"One thing which I like most in my work is the demand for regularly learning new things"

When a new problem or challenge is formulated, it takes time, and sometimes a lot of time, to find a solution. All this time is full with hard work,

individually or in teams, and for long periods it may look like no solution will be found. However, nothing can be compared to the exciting moment when a solution is found.

My favorite subject is mathematical modeling and computer simulation of industrial and environmental processes, especially in the case of multiscale and multiphysics problems. This is a rather broad subject, but unlike some colleagues in the University who can work all the life on one problem, my work requires collaboration with various industries on various processes and materials.

"With the creative and collaborative efforts of all involved partners, the bottlenecks are overcome"

What does your daily job look like?

The things which I like most in my work are the demand for regularly learning new things, the chance to work with young people, and the satisfaction to see how the industry is becoming more and more integrated with the research.

I cannot say that I have a typical day or week, but I have typical activities. The main ones are research on a new challenge or writing papers, project work or writing proposals/offers/reports, meetings with industrial and project partners, meetings with the students and postdocs, participation in conferences.

"Nothing can be compared to the exciting moment when a solution is found"

What excites you in the XERIC project?

I came in the project via contact with GVS and Genoa team. I have seen that a lot of preliminary work was already done, and the developments are mature for design, manufacturing of prototypes and testing.

The XERIC idea was exciting, the involved partners were highly competent, I saw that ITWM competence can really help in this project, so I jumped into the proposal preparation.

"My favorite subject is mathematical modeling and computer simulation of industrial and environmental processes"

What are, according to you, the major challenges to be overcome in XERIC?

Several challenges have been overcome, despite they required significant work. For example, in certain moment the situation with the design of the small prototype was critical. However, with the creative and collaborative efforts of all involved partners, the bottlenecks were overcome.

A big remaining challenge is the manufacturing of the required number of prototypes on a time schedule allowing their thorough testing.

"The XERIC idea was exciting, the involved partners were highly competent, I saw that ITWM competence can really help in this project, so I jumped into it."

Are you participating in other international projects? Can you talk about them and explain the role you play?

I am participating in several other national and international projects, and the role I play there is similar to the role I play in Xeric, just the processes/subjects and the challenges are different.

Thanks for your time Oleg. All the best for XERIC and your other projects!

Oleg's skills

Computer simulation; Mathematical modeling; Algorithms; Multiscale and multiphysics problems, Industrial filtration, Li-ion battery, Flow in porous media, CFD.

FRAUNHOFER - ITWM, a partner in the XERIC project

The Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics (ITWM - Germany) is one of the more than 60 institutes of the Fraunhofer Society for applied research. The ITWM has gained a high reputation in mathematical research for industrial and commercial applications.

ITWM's participation in XERIC is mainly driven by the department of Flow and Material Simulation (about 30 employees). ITWM is responsible for the design of a small scale prototype of the climate control system. ITWM is also involved in modelling efforts aiming at understanding, quantifying and thus preventing frost formation.

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European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Dr Fausto LENTINI**

New Products and Materials Researcher
at GVS S.P.A., Italy

Dr Fausto LENTINI

is an expert in filtration media and in automotive filters. Involved in the frame of XERIC, he is now assembling the 3F-CMC.

"XERIC is particularly interesting because it is a Green project"

Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself?

Yes, with pleasure! You already know my name. I'm forty years old and I live with my family in a small town near Bologna, but I come from Calabria, south of Italy. I graduated in materials science from the University of Calabria of Cosenza (UNICAL). I did my PhD thesis at the Institute on Membrane Technology of the National Research Council (ITM-CNR) on synthesis and characterization of organic and inorganic membranes.

I moved to Bologna in September 2006 and started my career at the GVS Company where I am still working in the R&D department as Project Manager. I am basically in charge of projects to develop filters for various key sectors, such as motor vehicles, healthcare or food industries.

What is appealing to you being a researcher? How challenging is it?

From my point of view, the biggest challenge for a researcher is to discover new technologies for the community. To do this, you have to remain curious, determined and sometimes courageous. I really like to work collaboratively to solve problems, developing filters in my actual position. I realize how lucky I am to do what I like for a job, as I think there are only few concrete opportunities for researchers in a context of limited financial capabilities.

What does your daily job look like?

I manage on average 8 projects per year, which include different stages and activities. Generally, once the work plan validated with my boss, I schedule the tasks autonomously. So, I try to mix experimental activities with desk job. In this way, the work is always interesting and all the activities are moving forward.

What excites you in the XERIC project?

XERIC is particularly interesting because it is a "Green project". Its focus is energy saving in electric vehicles, which deserves a round of applause and requires encouragement. I'm proud that GVS gave me the responsibility to manage the prototyping stage of the 3F-CMC.

"I really like to work collaboratively to solve problems, developing filters in my actual position."

What are you expecting from the project?

The main challenge to overcome is to show that, with an innovative system like the 3F-CMC, it is possible to increase the energy saving in electric cars. I hope our positive results would enable us to continue and expand our R&D work on innovative systems to save energy.

Thanks for your time Fausto and all the best for XERIC !

Fausto's skills

Filtration media; automotive filters

GVS, a partner in the XERIC project

GVS is a profitable business to business high-quality and high-volumes filter manufacturing company covering various markets, e.g. automotive but also healthcare, building, active filtration or safety. Started in 1979, it has now offices in major markets and 16 manufacturing sites located worldwide (Italy, UK, Brazil, USA, China, Rumania).

The company has more than 30 years of experience in the automotive business. GVS' automotive products cover all requirements of the market and are supplied worldwide to industry (80% of European cars use at least one filter from GVS). The know-how, resources and core business activities of GVS are directly related to the objective of XERIC. GVS supplies technical expertise and resources adequate to carry out the development and prototype preparation of hydrophobic membranes and membrane contactors (3F-CMC). Furthermore, the anticipated exploitation strategy of the project results fits well with the worldwide marketing and commercial capability of the company.

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